

Audience Perception of Media Portrayal of Women in Television Commercials

Sheidu Awodi

Department of Mass Communication, Achievers University, Nigeria
awodisheidu@gmail.com

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7890620

Abstract

This study examined audience perception of media portrayal of women in television commercials. The objectives of the study were to find out the audience perception of the type of portrayal given to female characters in television commercials and to ascertain the influence of television commercials on the audience's perception of women in real life. The study was anchored on cultivation theory. A quantitative descriptive survey was adopted for the study. Data were collected from three hundred and thirty (330) residents of Ayingba town in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi State. The findings revealed that there was a dominantly negative cum subjective portrayal of women in Television Commercials and there was a significantly harmful influence of such portrayal of women in Television commercials on the perception of women in real life. Therefore, it concluded that television commercials were used as tools of stereotype against the sociological representation of women. The study recommended among other things that television commercials copywriters and producers live up to their professional expectations of gender fairness, balance, and proper redirection of course in the light of the subject matter, women's depiction.

Keywords: Women, Portrayal, Perception, Television commercial, Audience

Background to the study

The mass media mirror the society wherein which they function. So, society dictates the functionality and/or modus operandi of the media. However, in the symbiosis between the two (media and society), the mass media are considered to possess enormous power in influencing the perception of the society through attitudinal judgment, status conferral, and inter alia stirring the public towards the certain course. In the words of Asemah et al. (2014), "the media can build up or break down, weaken or strengthen existing stereotypes". Explaining the power of the mass media in influencing desired and predetermined changes in society, Adegoreye (2015) writes that "the media are major carriers of culture, capable of promoting or influencing attitudes, motivating and fostering the speed of behaviour patterns and bringing about social integration."

One of the major issues being frowned upon at over the years concerns media and society in terms of gender inequality in media representation between male and female folks. Unarguably, the issue of gender inequality and marginalisation against women has remained controversial in almost every sector of society especially in Africa due to the patriarchal nature of her culture which gives men high social ranking (Anorwe et al., 2012). The media are supposed to be neutral and avoid all forms of stereotypes and are often subjected to aligning to this bias. Whether the media are playing this function of promoting equality is subject to argument. In terms of the argument of women-media portrayal, one could hastily dismiss such representation as simple but it is not as some studies such as Akinfeleye (2021), Ferrante (2018) and Barthel (2012) have linked the social experiences of women in the society to their media portrayal. So, whether women are seen and perceived in the right perspective as a human being as their male counterparts or not is a significant issue calling for scholarly re-attention.

According to Sinha (2020), a woman would be more comfortable if perceived as equal, as strong and as socially, politically and economically advantageous to men. Of course, women will be encouraged if perceived as intelligent, hardworking, imaginative, caring, socially relevant, etc as men. Stankwiewiez and Roselli (2018) argue that those who perceive women negatively know little of the link between the media and their perception. In reality, women performed the most tasking job to keep society and families' social functions. For instance, women carry pregnancy for nine months and yet do the household chores. Some of them still go to the farm to carry out some farming activities. The worry of the woman in recent times is because rather than address inequality, generations after generations until just towards the mid of twentieth century, appeared to

have been satisfied with seeing women as players of second fiddle to men. The pattern of practices that appear content with sees-women as mere appendages to the status of men can be traced to a universal phenomenon. So, it is inappropriate when women are perceived as second fiddle in the twenty-first century (Gulati, 2014).

As argued by Okunna (2016), women are perceived as being inferior and subordinate to their men counterparts. Both the educated and the illiterate alike treat women based on this stereotype. The woman is a defaced human nature and a mutilated male. This simple but inimical view about women has spread through all nations of the world and has come through centuries, perhaps, from the inception of time. Furthermore, the report of several broadcasts on Cable Network News (2016) suggests that “there is no place in the world where women are considered to be equal to men.” So, the issue of gender inequality is not a unique feature peculiar to any particular individual, institution or society. Salawu (2020) localises this argument and opines that gender inequality is a social reality which has long been accepted by both male and female subcultures of society.

Members of society are taught and shown their diverse places in the family and society according to their sex. Through the process of socialisation, the male child learns to be hegemonic and domineering over the female child who on the other hand is taught to be subservient under a man. Since it forms part of their upbringing, the male subspecies find themselves perpetuating the agenda of lording it over the female species. To buttress the fact that the issue of subjugation, domination, and marginalisation of women by men is a global issue, even in the western societies, the female, from the cradle is made to believe that they are cut for the softer roles (Courtney & Whipple 2015; Dominick & Rauch, 2015).

Most people all over the world now see the need for a change in the status quo. Civilisation and antecedents have proved wrong the perception that the place of the woman in the family and society is restricted to the background. Therefore, there have been craving and agitation for equality between men and women in society. And so, several theoretical, verbal and physical efforts have gone down the throat of the campaigns and crusades for the liberation and empowerment of women (Anyacho, 2017). In spite of all that has been said and done aiming at the emancipation of woman, there appears to be little or no change at all from the status quo. The question is: why is it so; is this what societies want after all? What are the factors that are sustaining this modus operandi and how far and well have the mass media gone and done in championing the course of the woman? In trying to provide an answer to these questions Barhel (2020) and Hentschell et al. (2019) attribute the persistent domination of women by men to the following factors like religious and cultural prejudices as well as male chauvinistic attributes. This means that emancipation for women might still be farfetched since the systematic structure which is purely pro-men in nature is still intact.

It could be drawn out from this position of Adegoreye (2015) that the media are remote causes of relegation of women to the background. In any case, however, the media ought to provide a voice to the decentred and downtrodden women. Azeez (2020) opines that the mass media have crucial roles in promoting human right as agenda setting on topical social issues of one of the media fundamental functions in the society. In light of the foregoing, Nigerian Television can serve as viable tools for creating awareness, educating the public and promoting the idea of the liberation and empowerment of women. In television commercials, it is recorded that the women used as a tools in advertising especially in television to attract, persuade, stimulate, and to sustain continuous patronage of the viewers or audience (Matthews, 2010). Therefore, the study looks at audiences’ interpretations of the representation of women in television commercials.

Statement of the problem

The issue of media insensitivity regarding the imbalance in the treatment of women portrayal has been a source of concern for decades and is still on. Media scholars such as Gulati (2014), Dominick and Rauch (2015), Okunna (2016), Stankwiewiez and Roselli (2018) and Azeez

(2020), among others, submit that the media of communications have not been fair to female folks. It has been observed that women are generally perceived as inferior to men who has made them subordinate to men. Some TV commercials had portrayed women negatively as a voiceless object in society, sex object, vulnerable and weak which has to always be at the mercy of men both educated and literate alike, and treats women the same. In evaluating the opinions of the audience on the interpretation and representation of women in television commercials, there is the possibility that being humans with diverse minds and modes of thinking and perception they tend to interpret them from different angles, while some might support the representation of women in television commercials on the basis that it promotes womanhood positively, others might be opposed to it on the basis that promoting women cheap. In light of this, the study finds it imperative to measure this trend; ‘is the representation of women in television commercials as interpreted on the positive or negative side?’ This is what this study sets out to determine.

Objectives of the study

This study aims to access audience perception of media portrayal of women in television commercials. This aim is however broken down into specific objectives, which are;

1. To examine audience perception of the type of portrayal given to women in Television Commercials.
2. To ascertain the influence of television commercials’ portrayal of women on the audience’s perception of women in real life

Scope of the study

By content, the study covers audience perception of media portrayal of women in television commercials. By duration, it covers the between 2021 to 2022 and by focus, it examines the perception of residents of Ayingba Town in Dekina Local Government Area of Kogi States for the sake of reach convenience, availability of respondents, and relevance to the issue under investigation.

Media and social perceptions

Perception is a formal process by which we become aware of changes through the senses of sight, hearing, etc. Perception is a process of analysing information gotten through the senses. But the validity of the judgment reached or formed at the end of the processing is usually subjective, that is, tied to the experience of the person who has either seen, heard or becomes aware of the data from the environment. This central understanding of the concept of perception is related to both philosophical and psychological meanings (Azeez, 2020).

Fill (2013) even treats the concept alongside its appearance in parapsychology. In that extended understanding, perception means a direct apprehension of states of affairs or things in a fashion not associated with any of the known senses. In this way, perception is extra-sensory perception which is clairvoyance (direct perception of the past or remote phenomenon), precognition (the direct perception of the future phenomenon), and telepathy (direct communication with another person without the use of known normal pathways). One of the clearest but most radical expression of the concept of perception came from George Barkeley in the 18th century in the attempt to define existence. Berkeley thought that for a thing to be, it has to be perceived. Anything that cannot be perceived cannot be said to exist. The typical formulation of his thesis according to Fill (2013) was ‘esseestpercipi’ (to be is to be perceived). What this means is that for anything, including an experience to exist, it has to be perceived by a knowing mind. So, perception is fundamental to existence. If humans were unable to perceive the existence of God, then, by this logic God would not have been said to exist.

Reflection on the thought of other thinkers concerning the issue of perception, Shimp (2020) showed that John Locke attributed the origin of perception to sensation or reflection, whereas “sensation is the immediate awareness of its internally generated ideas” (p. 82), but perceptions generally meet different hurdles in the process of knowing. Are our perceptions reliable? Can we

trust knowledge based on the senses? Some of the already identified include “misperception, illusion, deception, delusion, phantasmagoria as the endemic problems of perception” (p. 83). The consequence of this is that, what we claim to perceive may be wrong after all. For the moment, it may be safe to conclude that the fact that we can be mistaken about our perception rocks the boat of certainty in matters of knowledge (Ferrante et al. 2018). We know the fact of misjudgement, unreliable justification, deceitful appearance (mirage) and so on, are some of the giant standings on our way to reaching the land of certainty in matters of knowledge. How are we sure we ever perceive the real things, and that our accounts of them are true (Manish, 2012). The implication of perception to media messages is simply that human beings have limitations and are non-linear sensing mechanisms, and the characteristics of the human system must be taken into consideration when planning media programmes if dysfunctional emergent behaviour is to be minimised.

Perception variations are entirely based on audience characteristics and stereotyping. It is remarkable that that we have to end our exposition of perception on a sceptic note. This is to show that when we say audience perception of the portrayal of women in television commercials: we are not by any means taking it for granted that perception is a self-evident word, the meaning of which is understood by all who use it. But the thrust of this work is in discerning the content of true reflection of what happens in television commercials or not, is not the major preoccupation of the work.

Theoretical framework

The theoretical framework of this work is anchored on the cultivation theory which was developed by Georg Gerbner, Larry Gross, Michael Morgan, and Nancy Signorielli in 1976. This theory analyses the media’s role in the conceptualisation of social realities. According to the theorists, the theory posits that television is a socially transformative device because of its ability to guide cultural and social perceptions, and unity groups of people. This view aligns with Gebner’s position that suggests heavy television viewing results in accurate depictions of reality. It sees television as the most influential source, the most widely shared set of messages and images in our history which has become the most powerful source of socialisation by which most people from childhood imitate roles and standards as behaviours by influencing opinions, and shaping perspective (Gerbner & Gross, 1976). So, viewers of television cultivate attitudes due to their exposure to media and as such, it can be confidently concluded that the theory is applicable across all media forms. Although, the theory has been criticised for being over-simplistic and overly generalised as the study that gave birth to the theory was done using a child whose sense of decision is low (Higbee & Lim, 2019). However, the relevance of this theory to my work is that consumers of different products and services got exposed to television commercials with feminine roles through television viewing, and cultivate a new opinion, beliefs about women which out rightly influence their attitude towards them.

Methodology

The methodology is the practical, procedural and systematic operational plan or blueprint which a researcher intends to follow in accomplishing the objectives of the study. It is concerned with the ‘how’ rather than the “what” aspect of research. This study adopted a descriptive survey research design. This research surveyed some residents of Anyigba communities of Kogi State’s opinion on the representation of women in some television commercials. This made the research to be descriptive.

Population, sample size and sampling technique of the study

The population of this study comprises of residents of the Anyigba metropolis with a total population of 18,907 (Omatola et al., 2020) as projected from the 2006 general population census. It is chosen as a sample area because it is made up of people from different ethnic backgrounds and social classes. The sample size of the study was 334 as ascertained by Cochran’s sample

determination formula which is given as “N’ = estimated sample/ (1+estimated sample/population)”.

In terms of sampling technique, the multiple-stage sampling technique was adopted. In the first stage, the researcher made use of the simple random sampling technique through a raffle draw to select the communities for the study. Out of the entire fourteen communities in Anyibgba which are Oji-Ofu, Omedo, Abuja-Area, Obeya-Kekele, Obeya-Lile, University-Village, Ofe-Odu, Atane-Goma, Ajetachi, Iji, Ogane-aji, Kaduna–Efekepe, Anokwu, and GRA. The six communities picked at random were Ajetachi, Iji, Ogane-aji, Obeya-Kekele, Kaduna–Efekepe, and Anokwu. The last stage. Then, for each of the communities, the researcher selected 65, except for Kaduna–Efekepe, and Anokwu that had 66 each to make up the 392 which is the sample size for the study.

Instrumentation

The instrument of data collection was a self-designed questionnaire consisting of two parts - Part A contains the bio-data of the respondents and part B contains the questions with respect to the research objectives. For validity, relevant inputs and opinion experts in communication were sought address narrow and single view to the work as well as detects the grammatical, contextual, and mechanical error. The errors were corrected and the research method proved efficient as a research instrument for the study. For reliability, a pilot study was conducted with a questionnaire administered to four communities. These communities were conveniently selected because they were not among the 16 selected sample departments. A test-retest method of reliability was used with an interval of two weeks to establish the stability of the questionnaire over time. After correlating the first and second responses using Pearson Product Moment Correlation co-efficient formula, a reliability coefficient of 0.82 was obtained. This indicated that the questionnaire was reliable for obtaining information in this study.

Methods of data analysis

The researcher utilised face-to-face administration of the instrument and instant retrieval from respondents. The statistical instrument or tools used in analyzing the data will be frequency count, simple percentages and tables and mean scores.

Data presentation

A total number of 334 copies of questionnaire were distributed, three copies were not returned, and a copy out of the 331 copies that were retrieved, was invalid. Therefore, the analysis below is based on the 330 valid questionnaires.

Table 1: Demography of respondents

Community Distribution of Respondents	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ajetachi	54	16.4
Iji	55	16.7
Ogane-aji	56	17.0
Obeya-Kekele	56	17.0
Kaduna–Efekepe	54	16.4
Anokwu.	55	16.7
Total	300	100
Age (Years)	N	%
18-23	52	15.8
24-29	201	61.0
30-34	63	19.1
41-Above	14	4.2
Total	300	100
Marital Status	N	%
Single	278	84.2
Married	52	15.8
Separated/Divorced	0	0

Widowed	0	0
Total	300	100
Educational Qualification		
	N	%
FSLC	24	7.4
SSCE	88	27.2
OND/NCE	61	18.0
HND/ First Degree	121	37.5
MSC/PhD	37	11.0
Total	300	100
Occupation		
	N	%
Students	85	25.8
Farmers	43	13.0
Artisans	56	17.0
Traders	69	20.9
Civil Servants	77	23.3
Total	300	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From the above, it was shown that most of the respondents are between 21 – 30 years of age. It equally reveals that most of them (84.2%) are mostly single. They are majorly HND or Degree holders. The population is also dominated by students and civil servants.

Table 2: Type of portrayal of women in TV commercials

Frequency of Exposure to TV commercials	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Frequently	132	40%
Sometimes	125	37.9%
Rarely	41	12.4%
Not at all	32	7.7%
Total	330	100
Dominant Appeal of the Television Adverts/Commercials		
	N	%
Sex	255	73%
Fear	21	6.4%
Domestic Solution	42	12.7%
Violence	0	0%
Others	12	3.6%
Total	330	100%
Interpretation of the TV Commercials		
	N	%
Highly Objective	58	17.6%
Objective	41	12.4%
Rarely Objective	147	44.5%
Not Objective	84	25.5%
Total	330	100
Overall Views on how women are portrayed in the TV Commercials		
	N	%
Positive	76	23.0%
Negative	146	44.2%
Neutral	62	18.8%
I don't Know	46	13.9%
Total	330	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

The first item in Table 1 shows that the majority of the respondents have frequent exposure to the selected commercials which validate their responses or opinion on the subject under investigation. Secondly, it shows that the major appeal of TV commercials by women is dominated with sex appeal. The third Item reveals that the commercials are rarely objective. Finally, items four shows that the overall view of how women are portrayed in TV commercials is negative. Deductively, it can be submitted that there is the dominantly negative subjective portrayal of women in television commercials.

Table 3: Influence of TV commercial portrayal on perception of women in real life

Factors responsible for ways women are portrayed in adverts/commercials	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Ignorance	48	14.5%
Social Desirability	87	26.4%
Male Chauvinism	133	40.3%
Economic Factor	62	18.8%
Total	330	100
Dominant Role Played by Women in TV Commercials	N	%
Weaker Sex	54	16.4%
Domestic Servant	94	28.5%
Sex Object	128	38.5%
All of the above	54	16.4%
Total	330	100
Role of Women in Comparison to Men	N	%
Equal with Men	62	18.8%
Subordinate to Men	147	44.5%
Undetected	41	12.4%
Others	84	25.5%
Total	330	100
Level of the Influence of TV Commercial stereotypes on Perception of women in Real life	N	%
Positive	96	29.1%
Negative	126	38.2%
Neutral	62	18.8%
I don't Know	46	13.9%
Total	330	100

Source: Field Survey, 2022

From Table 3, the first item disclosed that the most dominant factor for the stereotypical presentation of women in TV commercials is male chauvinism. Secondly, it shows that the dominant role of women as held by the respondent is as sex objects. Thirdly, the table reveals that in comparison to men, women are portrayed to be subordinate to their male counterparts. Finally, the level of influence is to an extent. It reveals that there is significant negative influence of the portrayal of women in Television commercials on the perception of women in real life.

Discussion of findings

To achieve the aim of this study, two research objectives were set. The first finding of this study which is in line with first of the objective (type of portrayal given to the women in Television

Commercials) disclosed that majority of the respondents have significant exposure to television commercials. Deductively, with the audiences' level of familiarity, high exposure and understanding of television commercials. Then, a significant finding of the study shows that sex appeal constitutes the dominant advert appeal. This explains the lamentation of Azeez (2020) that the media portrayal of women projects more of women's sexuality than their value as a human should occupy a respectable positions in society. To him, hardly is there a television commercial with a woman as a director, an engineer, a politician, a senator, a governor or a president but mostly as models, dancers, passive or housewives. Then, the thematic perception of the audience shows that the female audience's interpretation of the selected commercial is that they are not objective, ineffective, and portrayed women in a negative light. This finding is also consistent with the conclusion of the (Okunna, 2016; Azeez, 2020) among other authors that the media portrays women stereotypically and negatively. Also, as Akinfeleye and Amebi (2021, p. 5) rightly pointed out; "commercials play the role of stereotype using portrayals to help shape perspectives on people's culture. To give more flesh and ground to the finding, the study revealed that the dominant role of women in the commercials is as sex objects. In the same light as this finding, Salawu (2020) submits that in most media productions, women play trivial, emotional and subordinate roles. In soap operas reinforce the work traditionally associated with women are the function of nurturing relationships and holding the family together.

This second finding of the study which is on the influence of television commercials on the audience perception of women in real life began with an inquiry into factor responsible for the ways women are portrayed in adverts/commercials and was revealed that male chauvinism dominate among ignorance, social desirability, and economic factors. This is in line with the position of Asemah et al. (2014) that the patriarchal nature of Nigerian society is being replicated in the portrayal of women in television commercials. In addition to this stand, the women play in television commercials as subordinate to men in most television commercials and are not in concordance with their natural role as women in real life. This buttresses the stand of Okunna (2016) that society relegates women to the background through cultural and religious systems in that the owners and users of the media alike are parts and parcel of the inimical makeup which is difficult the ancient chord of male domination over women. In line with a feminist's ideological perceptive of the media then the films position women at the bottom of power hierarchy in a way that reinforces their domination and suppression. So in most media contents, women play the trivial, emotional and subordinate role and as Courtney and Whipple (2015) noted "soap operas reinforce the work traditionally associated with women are the function of nurturing relationship and holding the family together. To further buttress this, Asemah et al. (2014) alarm that the struggle for women's emancipation is being eroded by the internalisation of the negative images of women in home videos/films, television programmes and commercials. This concurs with Akinfeleye and Amebi (2015), that the mass media plays the role of stereotype using portrayals to help shape perspectives, behaviour and culture of people toward a social group.

Conclusion and recommendations

The study examined the audiences' perception of media portrayal of women in television commercials and concludes that television commercials are viable tools for social construction. They can be used to champion good courses as well as negative courses. It is noticeable that women have been grossly marginalised in Nigerian societies just like in other African cultures. However, television commercials could be used to reposition women in society and alleviate their plights of suppression, relegation and subjugation under the claws of their men counterparts. Submissively, the study concludes that women are portrayed in negative light in television commercials (with most emphasis on their sexuality) which influences how are perceived and treated in society. This may be a function of male chauvinistic and hegemonic tendencies of the male folks who produce most of these adverts or commercials.

Based on the findings, the study recommends the following:

- i. Television commercials copywriters/producers should live up to their professional expectations of fairness and balance as there is a need for proper redirection of course in the light of the subject matter.
- ii. Women should go into television commercials production so that they could use the medium to create and sell their real image to the public as no one can understand or portray a realer picture of women than the women.
- iii. Government put up deterrent measures in form of strict censorship to ensure that there is a change of course regarding the portrayal of women in television commercials.
- iv. Women should campaign more rigorously against the numerous, cultural, religious, male chauvinistic, social, and economic practices or forces which are determinant factors for the negative portrayal of women in Nigerian television commercials.

References

- Adegoreye, K. (2015). *Gender integration into policy reforms in Nigeria*. Being a paper presented at the 1st Annual Murtala Mohammed Memorial conference held at ECOWAS Secretariat, Abuja.
- Akinfeleye, R. A., Amobi, I. T. (2021). Nollywood video films as a medium for reconstructing the African cultural identity. *Communication Review*, 5(1); 1-23.
- Anorwe, L. I., Obayi, P. M. & Onyebuchi, C. A (2012). Politics, mass media, gender Balance and politics in Nigeria: An assessment. *International journal of language literature and gender studies*. Bashir Dar Ethiopia, 1 (3).
- Asemah, E. S, Edegoh, L. O. N., & Ojih, E. U. (2014). Audience perception of the portrayal of women in television advertising. *An International Journal of Language, Literature and Gender Studies*. Bahir Dar, Ethiopia. 2 (1).
- Azeez, A. L. (2020). Audience perception of the portrayal of women in Nigerian home video films (Bsc. Project Research). Department of mass communication, University of Ilorin, Ilorin Nigeria.
- Barthel, D. (2020). Men, media and the gender order when men put on appearances. *Global Journal of commerce & Management perspective*.
- Courtney, A. E & Whipple, T. W. (2015). Female's role portrayals in advertising and communication effectiveness: *A review journal of advertising*, 14(3), 4-17.
- Dominick, J. R., & Rauch. U. (2015). The image of women's network TV commercials. *Journal of Broadcasting*, 16 (3), pp. 259-65.
- Ferrante, C. L., Haynes, A. M., & Kingsley, S. M. (2018). Image of women in television advertising. *Journal of broadcasting and electronic media*, 32(2), 231-237.
- Fill, C. (2013). *Marketing communications: Brands, experiences and participation*. (6th Ed.) England: Pearson Education Limited.
- Gulati, M. (2014). Analysis of projection of women in advertisements on society. *Global Journal of commerce & Management perspective*. 3(5).78-31
- Higbee, W. & Lim S. H. (2019). Concepts of transnational cinema: Towards a critical transnationalism in film studies. *Transnational cinemas* 1(1), 7-21.
- Idowu, W. (2021). Nigerian Citizenship, Gender and the Politics of Identity: the conflict between constitutionalism and conventionalism. *Brain field Law Journal*. 1(2).
- Hentschell, T., Heilman, E., Peus, C. V. (2019). *The multiple dimensions of gender stereotypes: a current look at men's and women's characterizations of others and themselves*. <https://www.frontiersin.org/articles/10.3389/fpsyg.2019.00011/full>.

- Manish, P. (2012). *Advertising appeals*. NBA eNotes. AIDA concept PPT business etiquettes. <https://www.enotesmba.com/2012/07/mba-notes>.
- Okunna, S. C. (2016). *Portrayal of Women in Nigerian home video films: Empowerment of subjugation*. www.jamr010003003.com.pdf adobe reader.
- Omatola, C. A., Onoja, B. A., Fassan, P. K., Osaruyi, S. A., Iyeh, M., Samuel, M. A. & Haruna, P. U. (2020). Seroprevalence of Chikungunya virus infection in five hospitals within Anyigba, Kogi State of Nigeria. *Brazilian Journal of Infectious Diseases*, 24(1). www.scielo.br.
- Salawu, A. (2020). Cultural Imperialism, Integration and Projection of Africa: Some emerging issues in the information media. *University of Nigeria Interdisciplinary Journal of communication Studies*. 2(1). <https://journal.ijcunn.com/index>.
- Shimp, T. A. (2020). *Integrated marketing communications in advertising and promotion*. (8th Ed.). China: Thomson South-Western.
- Sinha .P.C. (2020). *Global sourcebook on human rights*. Kanishka Publishers, New Delhi, India.
- Stankiewicz, J. M., & Roselli. F. (2018). *Women as sex objects and victims in print advertisement*. Online spring science Business media. <https://www.isarder.org>